

AGRONOMY FOR LANDSCAPING MOTORWAYS AND IRRIGATION SYSTEMS, AS WELL AS CREATING FLOWERBEDS OF VARIOUS SHAPES USING DECORATIVE ANNUAL AND PERENNIAL FLOWERS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the necessary agronomic and agro-technical principles for landscaping motorways. It examines various irrigation methods used in the greening of motorways, including simple surface irrigation, sprinkling, and drip irrigation, as well as the fog irrigation method used in greenhouses. The significance of simple irrigation and sprinkling methods for maintaining lawns located along motorways is discussed. Recommendations for tree care, pruning methods, and shaping are also provided.*

The article explores the design of flowerbeds, their geometric shapes, features of the color palette, and the selection of annual and perennial plants. Special attention is given to ensuring that the growth conditions of the plants correspond to the aesthetic aspects of the composition when creating flowerbeds.

Keywords: *landscaping, motorways, agronomic principles, agro-technical methods, irrigation, surface irrigation, sprinkling, drip irrigation, fog irrigation, lawns, tree care, pruning, shaping, flowerbed design, geometric shapes, color palette, annual plants, perennial plants, aesthetic aspects, composition.*

Introduction

Greening in urban environments plays a vital role in maintaining ecological balance and protecting the environment. It not only enhances the aesthetics of the city but also effectively contributes to nature conservation, improves air quality, and enhances climatic conditions. Care for plants, trees, and flowers in urban areas requires constant attention. In this process, the use of modern irrigation methods helps minimize negative impacts on the environment, conserve water resources, and promote balanced plant growth.

Organizing effective irrigation systems in cities requires addressing several technical and ecological challenges. Various irrigation methods, such as sprinkler irrigation, drip irrigation, and other modern technologies, help conserve water, improve plant care, and enhance soil condition. These methods are not only environmentally effective but also economically beneficial.

This research analyzes various aspects of greening and irrigation methods, their effectiveness, and their application in urban environments.

Research Methodology:

Literature Review: A review of existing scientific literature, articles, and publications related to urban landscaping and irrigation methods. This will allow the examination of modern approaches, analysis of existing methods, and identification of research gaps in the field.

Observation Method: Conduct observations of urban landscaping processes and irrigation techniques in various city areas. Assess the impact of different irrigation methods (e.g., sprinkler irrigation, drip irrigation, etc.) on water conservation, plant growth, and soil condition.

Experimental Method: Conduct comparative experiments with different irrigation methods to analyze their effectiveness. The main directions of the experiments will include:

- Measuring water consumption for each irrigation method.
- Monitoring the growth dynamics of plants using different methods.
- Evaluating soil conditions after irrigation.

Surveys and Interviews: Conduct surveys and interviews with experts in landscaping, agronomists, and gardeners. This method will gather expert opinions on the efficiency of irrigation methods and their adaptability to urban environments.

Statistical Analysis: Data collected during the experiments (water consumption, plant growth indicators, soil moisture) will be analyzed using mathematical and statistical methods. This process includes:

- Visualizing the growth dynamics of plants and water consumption in graphical form.
- Comparing the efficiency of each irrigation method.

Comparative Analysis: A comparative analysis of different irrigation methods in terms of ecological and economic efficiency. This analysis will assess the water-saving potential, additional costs, and environmental impact of each method.

Conclusions and Recommendations: Based on the research results, conclusions will be drawn about the efficiency of irrigation methods and their impact on urban landscaping. Additionally, recommendations will be provided on implementing water-saving and efficient irrigation methods in landscaping.

This research methodology will enable a comprehensive and precise analysis of the efficiency of irrigation methods used in landscaping and provide recommendations for the most effective methods from both ecological and economic perspectives.

The results obtained and their analysis.

Irrigation Methods in Greening

In the process of greening, various irrigation methods are employed, including simple surface irrigation (performed manually, with vehicles, or through irrigation ditches), sprinkler irrigation, drip irrigation, and misting (aerofogging) in greenhouses.

Simple Irrigation Methods

The simple irrigation method does not require complex engineering structures (such as water wells or pipelines) or only requires minimal amounts of them. This method allows irrigation to be carried out manually using special tanks or cisterns mounted on mechanical equipment, as well as through specially prepared irrigation ditches.

This method is particularly convenient for small areas and uncomplicated plots, as it enables effective irrigation of plants. Simple surface irrigation is typically used in vacant land or small gardens, leading to efficient resource utilization.

Sprinkler Irrigation

Sprinkler irrigation is used for larger areas, often effectively watering lawns along roadways, trees (such as firs), and flowers. This method significantly reduces manual labor and helps conserve water, making it efficient for extensive green zones. Sprinkler irrigation can be implemented through either stationary systems (when the system is installed in permanent locations) or movable systems, which utilize special mechanisms for relocating the equipment.

Drip Irrigation

Drip irrigation allows water to be delivered gradually and directly to the soil or plants. This method effectively utilizes water, maintains soil moisture, and is particularly advantageous for optimizing resource use in gardens and orchards.

Economic and Ecological Benefits

Choosing the right methods for greening is crucial for resource conservation, effective water use, and environmental protection. Each irrigation method has its positive and negative aspects, and it is essential to adapt them to address specific challenges and goals.

This research will analyze various methods of greening, their effectiveness, and their applications in urban environments.

1. Simple Irrigation Method

The simple irrigation method is one of the oldest and simplest ways to irrigate plants. This method can be carried out manually or with the help of mechanical means and is usually intended for small areas.

Characteristics:

Ease of Reuse: The simple irrigation method is easy and quick to execute, which helps save time.

Low Resource Consumption: This method does not require additional structures, making costs minimal.

Source Characteristics: Water sources (wells, rivers, ditches) may be needed for irrigation, but prepared water can be used instead.

Ease of Movement: The irrigation process is simple to move and manage.

Ease of Use: The simple irrigation method is easy to apply, especially for small personal gardens or large farming areas.

Practical Application:

The simple irrigation method is widely used in small gardens, vegetable patches, and for the care of various plants. This method meets the water needs of plants, ensuring their healthy growth and development.

Positive and Negative Aspects:

- **Positive Aspects:** The simple irrigation method promotes effective resource use, time savings, and convenience in plant care.

- **Negative Aspects:** However, there may be a loss of some water in this method, and it is important to always consider the needs of the plants. In some cases, insufficient water may be provided for the plants.

The simple irrigation method plays an important role in the greening process due to its advantages.

Sprinkler Irrigation

Sprinkler irrigation is commonly used for watering lawns along roadways, as well as for trees (such as firs) and flowers. This irrigation system significantly reduces manual labor and is highly effective in conserving water.

Mechanism of Sprinkler Irrigation

Sprinkler irrigation is implemented through pipes and specialized equipment. There are two main types of sprinkler irrigation systems: stationary and movable.

1. **Stationary Systems:** These systems are permanently installed in specific locations and provide consistent watering to designated areas. They are ideal for large lawns, parks, and landscaped areas that require regular irrigation.

2. **Movable Systems:** These systems utilize special mechanisms to relocate the irrigation equipment as needed. Movable sprinkler systems are particularly advantageous for larger green spaces where uniform and thorough watering is essential.

Benefits of Sprinkler Irrigation

- **Efficiency:** Sprinkler irrigation minimizes water wastage by directing water precisely where it is needed, ensuring that plants receive adequate moisture without excessive runoff.

- **Labor Savings:** This method reduces the amount of manual labor required for watering, making it easier for landscape maintenance.

- **Versatility:** Sprinkler systems can be adapted to various terrains and plant types, providing flexibility in irrigation planning.

Figure 2. Sprinkler irrigation

Overall, sprinkler irrigation is an effective method for maintaining green spaces, enhancing both aesthetic appeal and environmental sustainability.

During the rapid growth period of a tree, the care for its branches should be "expedited." In the maturity stage of the plants, the work of removing dry branches is carried out. Tree

pruning is performed by qualified and experienced horticulturists. Three types of pruning are used for branch care: formative, sanitary, and rejuvenating. The goal of formative pruning is to ensure the correct distribution of the main branches, to give the tree a beautiful and aesthetic appearance, to level its overall height, and to preserve both natural and artificial branches. When pruning a tree, the shape of its natural branching is taken into account: cylindrical, pyramidal, oval, and others. Each tree has its unique height and shape, and it is unacceptable to interfere with their pruning. Formative pruning involves trimming and shortening shoots as well as reducing branching. These works begin in nurseries.

The movable irrigation system consists of pipes installed on movable supports, special mechanisms, water pumps, and irrigation equipment.

Figure 3. Moving sprinkler irrigation

A flowerbed is a flower arrangement of a simple geometric shape, such as a circle, square, oval, and others. Flowerbeds can differ in style, color palette (colorful, monochrome, harmonious, or contrasting), and the "set" of plants used. In their design, both annual and perennial plants can be utilized, and herbaceous plants can be mixed with shrubs and trees. The most important aspect is selecting plants that are similar in growing conditions. Flowerbeds are positioned as the central element of the composition. Grass can be used as a background. The center of the flowerbed rises to 50-60 cm, while the edges rise to 8-10 cm, and it can be decorated with various stones. Flowerbeds are divided into flowering and herbaceous types. Herbaceous flowerbeds consist of low-growing, leafy, and ornamental plants. Flowering flowerbeds are composed of plants that bloom continuously. Tall and brightly colored flowers are placed in the center of the flowerbed, while shorter plants are positioned at the bottom.

Fig. 2.9 Construction of flower beds in various forms

Summary. The article examines essential agronomic and agro-technical principles for landscaping along motorways, focusing on various irrigation methods, including surface irrigation, sprinkling, drip irrigation, and fog irrigation in greenhouses. It highlights the importance of simple irrigation techniques for maintaining roadside lawns and offers recommendations for tree care, pruning, and shaping. Additionally, the design of flowerbeds is discussed, including their geometric shapes, color palette, and the selection of annual and perennial plants, emphasizing the need for alignment between plant growth conditions and aesthetic composition.

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